

Preparation of Anhydrous Halides of Lanthanides. Part I: Preparation of Anhydrous Halides of Lanthanum and Cerium (III)

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A brief but critical review of the method of preparation of lanthanum and cerium (III) halides is given. Anhydrous halides of these metals have been prepared by a new method in which suspension of the respective acetate in toluene or benzene is successively saturated with dry ammonia and anhydrous halogen hydric acid gas followed by isolation of the complex ammonium lanthanide halide and sublimation of ammonium halide therefrom. The yields are almost quantitative. However, pure iodides could not be prepared by this method.

The importance of the preparation of anhydrous lanthanide halides cannot be over-emphasised and there is a large body of literature¹ concerned with their preparation. The chlorides are widely used for the production of metals both by electrolytic and metallothermic methods. These are also utilised as source materials in the electromagnetic isotope separators and for thermo-chemical and physico-chemical studies of lanthanide compounds particularly in non-aqueous solutions.

Lanthanide halides when isolated from aqueous solutions usually retain 6 to 7 molecules of water. Most of this water can be removed by dehydration below 100°. However, it is difficult to remove the last molecules of water without causing decomposition of the halides. The methods reported for the preparation of anhydrous lanthanide halides have been summarised in a recent review¹.

The procedure of Brauman and Takvorian² for the preparation of anhydrous chlorides of lanthanum, neodymium and samarium by passing dry hydrochloric acid gas through a suspension of their benzoylates in ether has been reported not to work well in the hands of Taylor³. In the present investigation an effort has been made to evolve an easily workable procedure for the preparation of anhydrous halides of lanthanum and cerium (III). The iodides, however, could not be prepared as the replacement of the acetate group is not complete.

EXPERIMENTAL

An all glass apparatus with interchangeable standard joints was used and care was taken to exclude moisture during the performance of these experiments.

Thiophene-free redistilled benzene and toluene were kept over sodium wire. Pyridine and α -picoline were purified by keeping them over potassium hydroxide beads

1. Taylor, *Chem. Rev.*, 1962, **62**, 503.
2. Brauman and Takvorian, *Compt. rend.*, 1932, **194**, 1579.
3. Taylor, *Chem. Rev.*, 1962, **62**, 507.

for 24 hours and then refluxing for over an hour. They were distilled and fractions for use were collected at the following temperatures:

Pyridine: 112-113°/740 mm.

α -Picoline: 125-126°/740 mm.

Lanthanum acetate⁴ was prepared by refluxing lanthanum oxide with acetic anhydride. Cerium (III) acetate⁵ was obtained by the reaction of acetic anhydride on hydrated cerous nitrate. Perfectly dry hydrochloric⁶ and hydrobromic⁶ acid gases were prepared by the reported methods. Hydriodic acid gas was obtained by dropping saturated solution of potassium iodide over chilled phosphorus pentoxide. The gas was dried by passing it through a column (one foot) packed with phosphorus pentoxide. The gas thus obtained was tested to be anhydrous. Dry ammonia gas was obtained by warming liquor ammonia and passing it through a column packed with a mixture of sodium hydroxide beads and lime.

Halogen content was determined by Volhard's method⁷. The metal content of the compounds was estimated by precipitating it as an oxalate by the addition of a saturated solution of oxalic acid and igniting the precipitate at 850-900° to La_2O_3 and CeO_2 respectively.

Preparation: Two methods were tried.

1. Anhydrous halogen hydracid gas was passed through a suspension of lanthanide acetate. $\text{Ln}(\text{OAc})_3$, (2 g.) in benzene or toluene (50 ml.) for about half an hour. The contents were kept at the boiling point of the solvent during the passage of the gas. The product was allowed to stand for about 4 hours. After decanting off the solvent the solid residue was washed twice with petroleum ether and was subjected to vacuum to (using water-bath for warming) remove the volatiles. The products obtained were not pure. Complete replacement of OAc^- by halide ion has not been effected and the liberated acetic acid could not be removed.

2. Through a suspension of lanthanide acetate (2 g.) in benzene or toluene (50 ml.) dry ammonia gas was passed for about 20 minutes at room temperature. The contents were allowed to stand for about 4 hours. Halogen hydracid gas was then passed through the above suspension for about an hour and the contents were kept for some time. The solvent was decanted off and the product after washing twice with petroleum ether, was subjected to vacuum to remove the traces of the solvent. Finally the compound was purified from free as well as combined ammonium halides by subjecting it to high vacuum ($\sim 10^{-3}$ mm.) at 250-270°. Analytical results are summarised in Table I.

When the above reactions as described under (2) were repeated in the presence of amines such as pyridine and α -picoline, etc., added quantitatively to lanthanide acetate (1:1), instead of ammonia the complexes of the type $\text{Amine H}^+(\text{LnX}_4)$ were formed which when subjected to high vacuum ($\sim 10^{-3}$ mm.) at 250-260°, gave pure anhydrous halides in quantitative yields.

4. Seaton, Sherif and Audrieth, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1959, 9, 222.

5. Pande and Patnaik, *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 33, 877.

6. Vogel, 'Practical Organic Chemistry', Longmans Green & Co., 3rd Ed. (1956), pp. 179, 182.

7. Vogel, 'A Text book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis', Longmans Green & Co., 3rd Ed. (1961), p. 226.

TABLE I

Preparation of anhydrous halides by procedure II

Carboxy- late	Halogen acid gas	Analysis						Probable Formula
		Metal			Halide			
		% Found	% Calculated		% Found	% Calculated		
La (OAc) ₃	HCl	56.90	56.24	56.60	49.05	49.23	43.40	LaCl ₃
La (OAc) ₃	HBr	36.57	36.24	36.67	62.70	62.98	63.33	LaBr ₃
La (OAc) ₃	HI	27.80	28.01	28.60	64.66	64.95	65.36	LaI ₃ (OAc) ₃
Ce (OAc) ₃	HCl	56.50	56.09	56.82	42.92	42.75	43.18	CeCl ₃
Ce (OAc) ₃	HBr	35.98	36.40	36.85	63.25	63.65	63.15	CeBr ₃
Ce (OAc) ₃	HI	33.85	34.37	33.43	46.05	46.29	45.45	CeI ₃ (OAc) ₃

DISCUSSION

Technique of the method lies in the fact that this provides a novel method for the preparation of the double salts of the lanthanides with ammonium halides and amine hydrates without any water of crystallisation. The procedure gives products of high grade purity and involves simple techniques. Hence it can be described as the simplest and the cheapest method for the preparation of anhydrous lanthanum and cerium (III) chlorides and bromides. Efforts are being made to find the conditions for the preparation of anhydrous iodides by this method or by some modification of it.

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